

Fish-Induced Bias in Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler Data

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Abstract—ADCP measurements assume acoustic reflection from plankton and other small objects flowing passively with the current. We find that this assumption is in general valid, based on comparisons of the ADCP time series with data from 5–7 companion Vector Averaging Current Meters (VACMs) and Vector Measuring Current Meters (VMCMs) on moorings in the equatorial Pacific. However, a few months after deployment, ADCP speeds at some depths and locations can be biased low relative to those of the VACM/VMCMs. The characteristics of this bias are that it is most pronounced during daylight and in the upper 100 m. These characteristics lead us to suspect that the acoustic signals are being biased by returns from pelagic fish which are known to aggregate around floating objects, and which are frequently observed around the moorings on recovery/deployment cruises.

To investigate the possible impact of free swimming fish, and to determine sampling methods that might alleviate the observed ADCP speed bias, single-ping data were recorded for a 6-hour period immediately prior to recovery of a mooring at 0°, 110°W in October 1991. This was a time when the ADCP was reporting low speeds relative to a real-time VMCM near the surface. Post-recovery inspection of these data showed large beam-to-beam differences in acoustic echo intensities due to sporadic increases of up to 50 db in individual beams. Ensemble averages computed from the single-ping data showed velocity biases similar to those computed by the ADCP in the normal operational mode. Ensemble averages were then recomputed after omission of velocity values associated with high beam-to-beam echo intensity differences. This method of computation significantly reduced the bias, although some ensembles were lost due to an insufficient number of samples after editing. A modification to the ADCP firmware to perform beam intensity checks before computing ensemble averages has been developed in collaboration with RD Instruments, the manufacturer of our ADCPs. This firmware modification is currently being tested.

I. INTRODUCTION

Shipboard and moored Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) have become widely used in studies of ocean circulation. The principles of operation are fairly simple. An acoustic pulse is transmitted into the ocean and the time of returning pulses and the Doppler-shifted frequency of the returning pulses are measured. The time of return gives the distance to the acoustic targets and the Doppler frequency is proportional to the radial velocity difference between the instrument and the targets. In practice these measurements require sophisticated electronics and software and assumptions about the surrounding physical environment. One such

assumption is that the objects from which the pulses are reflected are either passively flowing with the surrounding water or that the net motion of a group of scatterers within the acoustic beam is equal to that of the surrounding water. In most cases this is a good assumption, but in our use of moored PROTEUS ADCPs we have found this assumption to be violated at times.

The PROTEUS (PROfile TElemetry of Upper ocean currentS) mooring was developed as part of the Tropical Ocean-Global Atmosphere (TOGA) program [1]. TOGA is a multi-national, 10-year program to study short-term climate variability associated with the El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) phenomenon. A goal of TOGA is the prediction of short-term climate variability based on dynamical coupled ocean-atmosphere models. Real-time equatorial current profiles are required for the development of these models since the upper-ocean circulation largely determines the evolution of ENSO-related SST anomalies and therefore air-sea interaction in the tropical oceans.

The need for real-time telemetry required the mounting of an ADCP on a moored surface buoy. The fiberglass toroid buoy that Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory (PMEL) has been deploying on equatorial moorings since 1976 was modified to support a downward looking 150-kHz RDI ADCP. Ensemble averaged profiles computed from 360 samples taken over a 6-minute period were computed hourly and recorded internally. The ADCP was programmed for bin widths and pulse lengths of 8 m. A total of 37 bins centered from 14 m to 302 m were sampled and recorded internally. Horizontal velocity from the uppermost 30 bins were transferred from the ADCP to a microprocessor mounted on the buoy once per hour. The microprocessor computed daily means from the hourly ensembles and transmitted them to shore via Service Argos. The first PROTEUS was deployed in April 1990 as a stand-alone mooring near 0°, 140°W. A traditional PMEL mooring with seven mechanical current meters (EG&G VMCMs at 10 m and 250 m, VACMs in between) was placed 17 km to the east. Six months later the moorings were recovered and replaced with a single PROTEUS mooring with seven mechanical current meters below the ADCP (VMCM at 3 m, 6 VACMs below). The site continues to be occupied with a replacement schedule of 6 months and an array of PROTEUS moorings has been created with the addition of moorings near 0°, 110°W, 0°, 165°E and 0°, 156°E.

Comparison of the mean speed profile from the ADCP and the four VACMs from which complete records were obtained is quite good (Fig. 1). VACM means exceeded the ADCP in all four cases. Differences ranged from 1 cm s^{-1} at the 25 m VACM (22 m ADCP) to 8 cm s^{-1} at the 80 m VACM (78 m ADCP). The ADCP bin depths have not been corrected for variation in speed of sound from the assumed value. Preliminary estimates from CTD data taken over a 10-year period at this site indicate that bin depths would be 4 m deeper at 100 m and 6 m deeper at 200 m. Making these corrections would not change which ADCP depth bins were nearest the VACM depths. ADCP velocities also have not been corrected for the speed of sound at the instrument heads since this correction would be on average only 0.05% of the measured speeds.

Some of the speed differences can be attributed to the differences in the measurement methods between instruments: the ADCP values are a mean weighted at the mid point of a 16-m wide bin while the VACM measures at a single point which is not necessarily the mid point of the ADCP bin. In

Fig. 1. Mean current speed from May 1990 to November 1991 at 0° , 140°W . Continuous line is for ADCP data with center of depth bins indicated with dot. Triangles are for VACM data that span the entire period.

Fig. 2. Contour plot of VACM (upper) and ADCP (lower) zonal velocity. Contour interval is 30 cm s^{-1} with westward contours dashed and lightly shaded. Regions of eastward flow greater than 90 cm s^{-1} are heavily shaded. Daily averaged data have been smoothed with 15-day Hanning filter. Symbols on the right axis of the VACM plot indicate the depth of instruments from which this plot was based.

addition, VACMs are known to overestimate velocity due to overspinning of the rotor in response to mooring motion. The VACM/ADCP differences here are of comparable magnitude to those between VACM/VMCM pairs on similar equatorial moorings [2].

Comparison of the temporal variability of zonal velocity is also quite good (Fig. 2). Many of the differences can be ascribed to the coarser vertical resolution of the VACM/VMCM data. For example, maxima and minima are stronger in the ADCP data and the core depth of the Equatorial Undercurrent (EUC) varies annually in the ADCP data between 94 m and 158 m while in the VACM/VMCM data it remains at 120 m.

Closer inspection of daily averaged time series show more significant velocity differences. For example, in December 1990 and again in October 1991 the 78 m VACM speed exceeded the 80 m ADCP by 50 cm s^{-1} (Fig. 3). The occurrence and magnitude of these negative differences decrease at 120 m and are absent at 200 m. We propose that these differences are due to bias induced by the reflection of the ADCP signal from fish schooling near the moorings and give evidence for this in the next section. Evidence of free-

Fig. 3. Daily values of ADCP-VACM speed difference.

swimming organisms affecting ADCP measurements has been observed by others. In one case, bias of shipboard ADCP measurements was detected at sunrise and was attributed to coherent movements of seamount-associated micronekton [3].

The source of the equally large but positive differences (i.e., ADCP velocity larger than VACM/VMCM velocity) at 78 m in March–April 1991 are as yet undetermined. However, this VACM was heavily fouled on recovery, which could have caused the instrument to underestimate current speed towards the end of the deployment.

II. REFLECTIONS FROM FISH AS SOURCE OF BIAS

The reflection of acoustic energy by fish as a source of these large velocity differences was first suggested by the manufacturer of the ADCP, RD Instruments. Fish are known to aggregate around surface moorings in general [4]; in our case we typically observe fish (predominantly yellowfin tuna with sharks and other large pelagic fish to a lesser extent) in abundance near the surface around moorings on recovery. In addition, [4] has documented diurnal patterns in the attraction of tuna to fish aggregating devices (FADs). They found that tuna tend to remain upstream and close to the devices during the day and to move away at night. They also noted a relationship between temperature and daytime vertical distribution of tuna around FADs.

If fish were distributed uniformly around a mooring and were attempting to remain near the mooring in the presence of a non-zero current, their velocity (lower than the surrounding water) would dominate the signal and the ADCP would compute a low-biased horizontal velocity. A similar

result would occur if a fish were sensed in the main lobe of one beam and were strong enough to be sensed in the side lobes of the other three beams. If the signal was much stronger than that of the surrounding water, horizontal velocity would tend towards zero and vertical velocity would be large. Alternatively, if a fish were in only one beam and generated an echo intensity similar to the surrounding water large vertical and error velocities would be computed and horizontal velocities would be biased low.

The times of large velocity differences, December 1990 and October 1991 (Fig. 3), are coincident with times of large differences in beam-to-beam intensity (Fig. 4). These differences, hereafter referred to as echo intensity range (EIR), were computed by differencing the minimum and maximum of the four beam intensities. Vertical velocity shows a similar, but less striking, correspondence and error velocity appears unrelated to velocity differences. The variability has some interesting features. During the first 6-month deployment in which the ADCP and VACM/VMCMs were on separate moorings EIR was consistently small. About 1 month after replacement by a unified mooring (deployed on October 27, 1990) EIR increased dramatically. After the third deployment (on May 8, 1991) EIR was relatively small for about 4 months after which it again increased dramatically. The fact that large EIR does not appear until 1 to 4 months after deployment may indicate that a certain time is required in which to develop a biosystem attractive to fish.

Fig. 4. Daily values of ADCP echo intensity range and depth of the 24°C isotherm (bottom panel).

Alternatively the timing may be associated with an annual or interseasonal variation such as mixed layer depth. It is curious to note that the 24°C isotherm (which is typically near the top of the thermocline) has a maxima coincident with large EIR (Fig. 4), although we know of no reason why the two should be related.

We do not believe that the large EIR during the second and third deployments are due to the ADCP reflecting from the in-line VACMs for several reasons: the differences are not consistently there; the cross-sectional area of the VACM seen from above forms a relatively small acoustic target and the VACMs are well within the sidelobes of the signal; the ADCP velocity profiles do not change dramatically between levels where VACM/VMCMs are present and where they are absent (e.g., Fig. 1). The absence of large EIR during the first deployment when there were no instruments below the ADCP is probably coincidence.

The above discussions have dealt with daily averaged data. The hourly ensembles give further evidence that the velocity differences are due to returns from fish. During the week of December 8 through December 15, 1990, when daily velocity differences were large, hourly differences were consistently large near mid-morning and consistently near zero during early evening (Fig. 5). EIR was also larger in the daytime than at night. This is consistent with [4]'s finding that tuna tend to leave the vicinity of a mooring at night.

The hourly averages recorded by the ADCP are ensemble means of 360 pings taken over a 6-minute interval. As such there is no way to identify individual pings that have been affected by reflections from fish. If a method of fish-affected ping identification were possible then such pings could be removed from the ensemble averages. To investigate this possibility we set a moored ADCP at 0°, 110°W to 2-second continuous sampling with no ensemble averaging for the last 6 hours of a 164-day deployment. Diurnal variation in EIR similar to that experienced at 0°, 140°W had been present in

Fig. 5. Hourly values of ADCP-VACM speed difference (upper) and ADCP echo intensity range at 78 m depth and 0°, 140°W. Nighttime (6 am to 6 pm local) is shaded.

Fig. 6. Distribution of ADCP echo intensity range by depth at 0°, 110°W for 6 hours of 2-second single-ping data.

the previous week, although with less regular variation in speed difference. Unfortunately, during the time of the single ping experiment speed differences were relatively small, the largest being at 46 m where the VACM mean speed exceeded the ADCP by 13 cm s⁻¹ over the 6-hour period.

The depth distribution of EIR was similar to that found at 0°, 140°W: large near the surface and smaller at depth (Fig. 6). The highest percentage of EIR was around 10 db at all depths, which may be taken as an estimate of background EIR noise level. At 110 m 88% of EIR was 15 db or less and values rarely exceeded 20 db, while at 46 m only 51% of EIR was 15 db or less and it exceeded 50 db at times.

The vast majority of large EIR is the result of large echo intensity in beam 1 or beam 4 (Fig. 7). EIR levels above 15 db were in more than two beams at once for 6% or less of the time. The current direction and buoy orientation (based on ADCP compass readings) were fairly stable during the 6-hour experiment. Beams 1 and 4 were typically on the upstream side of the buoy (Fig. 8). This orientation of the affected beams is consistent with earlier results [4] that tuna tend to stay upstream of FADs.

III. A FISH-BIAS REJECTION ALGORITHM

An algorithm was created to test whether differences between ADCP and VACM/VMCM velocities would decrease if the ADCP means were computed after rejecting values which could be tagged as being contaminated with energy returned from fish. Before using velocity data at a given bin the EIR was computed and if it exceeded a set value the

Fig. 7. Distribution of ADCP echo intensity at 46 m for each beam at 0° , 110°W for 6 hours of 2-second single ping data.

Fig. 8. Schematic drawing of mean orientation of ADCP and current at 46 m during 6-hour single-ping experiment. ADCP compass is mounted such that compass reading is direction in which head 3 is pointing. Error values are one standard deviation.

velocity data were not used in the ensemble average. The EIR at the next level up are also checked since echo intensity is sampled near the end of a bin. If fewer than 25% of the values in a 15-minute period were good the average was flagged as bad. The sequence was then repeated for each bin. This algorithm was used to compute 15-minute velocity averages from the 2-second data for comparison to 15-minute VACM averages. Maximum allowable EIR (MIR) was set at 15 db, 20 db or 25 db.

Speed differences between ensemble averaged VACM and ADCP time series were significantly reduced after application of this algorithm (Fig. 9). Differences at 46 m were most improved, dropping from 13 cm s^{-1} to near zero when MIR was set at 15 db. Unfortunately this was accompanied by more than 30% loss of data at shallow depths in the 15-minute time series due to there being less than 25% good data per average. In addition, percent good levels dropped below 80% below 90 m depth—a region where there is little evidence of returns from fish (Fig. 9). This result, along with the distribution of EIR (Fig. 6), indicates that 15 db may be too low a level for MIR. When set at 20 db percent good exceeds 95% below 90 m and data losses in the 15-minute time series are less than 20% at all depths. At this MIR level speed differences are 5 cm s^{-1} or less, which is within differences expected due to VACM rotor overspeeding.

Fig. 9. Left: Depth distribution of percent good per 15-minute ensemble average after fish rejection algorithm has been applied to 2-second single ping data. Means are over 6 hours. Solid black line indicates 100% good data. MIR levels (see text) are 15 db (dotted), 20 db (dashed) and 25 db (grey). Right: Depth distribution of ADCP-VACM speed difference for 15-minute ensemble averages. Black line is without application of fish rejection algorithm. MIR levels are as for left panel.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The source of ADCP bias towards low velocity when compared to mechanical current meters has been shown to be the contamination of the ADCP signal by the return of acoustic energy from fish. Evidence to support this include (1) increased levels of echo intensity range (EIR) during times of large bias, (2) diurnal periodicity in both velocity and EIR and (3) the tendency for increased echo intensity to be upstream from the mooring. An algorithm for real-time rejection of velocity bias due to fish has been developed and has been shown to significantly reduce the level of velocity bias. A similar algorithm has been incorporated into the ADCP software by RD Instruments and is currently being field tested.

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